

MENTAL EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation. For the modern educational system, the problem of mental education is very important. Scientists believe that the current millennium is celebrated with the information revolution, educated and educated people are valued as real national wealth. Currently, the task of forming the ability to active mental activity comes to the fore.

Keywords: preschool education, upbringing, mental development, mental education, mental work, book, knowledge, qualifications, skills.

The results of pedagogical and psychological studies show that preschool childhood is the optimal period in the mental development of a person. A number of psychological studies have shown that the level of mental development of preschool children is very high compared to later age periods. Any defects in upbringing in preschool childhood, in fact, are difficult to eliminate in adulthood and negatively affect the entire further development of the child. Local psychologists have noted that the most effective mental development occurs under the influence of education and education (L.S.Vygotsky, A.V.Zaporozhets, N.N.Poddyakov, D.B.Elkonin). The complete mental development of a preschool child is the most important indicator of its preparation for school.

The object of study is the mental education of preschool children.

The purpose of the study is to study the meanings, tasks and means of mental education of preschool children.

Hypothesis: the mental education of preschool children has specific tasks, and a certain set of tools is used.

Reason is the sum of cognitive processes that, in a broad sense, begin with perception and perception and include thinking and life.

Mental education is the systematic and objective pedagogical impact on young people in order to develop intelligence. He is a socio-tari of the younger

generation, embodied in the knowledge, skills and skills that humanity has accumulated, in the rules hi occurs as a planned process of acquiring experience.

This effect is carried out by adults and involves the creation of a variety of tools, methods, conditions that ensure the mental development of children. The mind of a person, his mental development, is manifested in the volume, character and content of knowledge. They find their expression in the enthusiasm of mental activity, in the pursuit of independent creative knowledge. Mental activity requires that attention be focused on the bar. The mind of a person is determined by the nature of his success in his main activities.

Berunius ' idea of ways to acquire knowledge is also relevant for the early period. Not to bore them when giving knowledge to students; continuity, consistency, the fact that new topics should be paid attention to interesting, mainly visual statements, etc. From those cases when the scientist could not perceive the soul badly to the connoisseurs. from vain competition. it became necessary to avoid fame. Berunius emphasizes the importance of three things in human maturation. This is heredity, environment, upbringing. Ibn Sina challenges humans to acquire knowledge, which is considered the first criterion for maturation. People without knowledge will be ignorant, they will not be able to know the truth, they say immature people. Ibn Sina considers it necessary to educate children in school in obtaining knowledge.

He emphasizes the need to comply with the following requirements in education: not to suddenly focus on the book in giving the child knowledge. giving knowledge by going from light to heavy in education, the exercise to be carried out is appropriate for the age of the child, paying attention to teaching team boMib in teaching, taking into account the interest and ability of the child in giving a curse, taking the training together with the physical exercise. Abu AM Ibn Sino developed the developmental stages of AQI. The first stage of perception with musokhada is the explanation of mental categories. Second stage. Perception of two different thoughts. Stage three. Acquired knowledge is achieved by the perception of the tikriar. Then it is called real intelligence. Since the scientist divided the mind into 3 boskicks, he meant children who could memorize at the first stage, but Hali could not write either letters or letters. In the second stage, the mind of children who begin to draw sticks, train the use of a pencil, the imagination begins to creak. In the third stage, a person will acquire the shakhls of the mind and the emotional images that accompany them. By reason, Ibn Sina understands the innate talent of Man, the ability to fixate, which is formed in the process of cognition.

In the content of mental education, its important component was distinguished, which is characterized by the formation of visual-effective and visual-figurative thinking in preschool children. Images of children reflecting this connection of phenomena are used to integrate individual specific knowledge into a specific system [28].

The period of pre-operator thinking corresponds to the age of the child from 2 to 7 years. During this period, fundamental changes occur in the general development of the child. A number of studies have shown that the most important forms of thinking of a preschool child are visual-effective and visual-figurative. The development of these forms largely determines the success of the transition to more complex, conceptual forms.

Thus, the mental, including mental, development of a child acts as a process with a clear historical and social character, all its main stages are determined by the peculiarities of the transmission of social experience.

The means of mental education of preschool children are significantly expanding. The teacher organizes various children's games, conducts observations, teaches counting, drawing, modeling, speech in the classroom. In the process of domestic activities, adults teach children to use various things, to work. Parents and teachers constantly put practical, game and cognitive tasks in front of the child, the solution of which leads to the formation of knowledge and skills, cognitive processes and abilities, the development of various types of activities, motives of cognitive activity, further improvement. speech, etc.

The basis of the child's mental development is his active activity. But this activity itself is formed, formed under the influence of education and upbringing.

Thus, adults, educators are faced with two tasks: in the implementation of mental education, directing their efforts to the formation of various types of activities that exist in children of a certain age, and using them for the purpose of mental education of the child.

At an early age, communication and play are formed on the basis of objective activity, and the beginning of Labor appears. Their further development occurs in preschool childhood .

The main activity of preschool children is play. At an older preschool age, the importance of educational activities increases. Visual activity goes a long way in development: the child acquires various skills and abilities in modeling, drawing and appliqué. Elementary musical activity is added to them - singing, listening to music, moving to music. It is formed into independent activities at preschool age and towards the end of design.

Children master different types of Labor - self-service, domestic, manual labor, labor in nature, etc. Sports activities are born in the depths of outdoor games and physical education classes.

Thus, at preschool age, the formation and development of the main types of human activity begins: communication, play, Education, Labor, art, sports.

By its nature, children's games are reflective activities. In the basic form of the game - a role - playing game with a plot, creative - children's impressions of the surrounding life-their knowledge, understanding of what is happening and events are reflected.

In a large number of games, Rules, various knowledge, mental operations, actions that children need to master. Mastering this goes hand in hand with general mental development, while this development is carried out in the game.

Mental education and development of a child in a creative game. The development of the content of creative games reflects the direction of children's cognition. The main content of children's plot games is the image of various actions with objects. In the process of such games, children master socially strict ways of using objects, actions with them. There is a generalization of actions and their separation from a specific object in the child's mind.

The appearance of the role in the game means changing the direction of the child's consciousness, his practical knowledge of the world around him. In the center of knowledge stands adults. The first role-playing games still reflect actions with objects, but now these actions and objects are associated with a particular person

Throughout the history of the development of the theory and practice of mental education of preschool children, the main efforts of psychologists are aimed at studying the problem of perception and the formation of conceptual thinking of preschool children. The mental education and development of the child was considered as a process of gradual introduction of the main forms of thinking - from emotional-practical to abstract-conceptual. At the same time, mental development acted not only as a process of mastering the knowledge and methods of mental activity of the child, but also as the formation of certain personality traits. The social environment, communication and activities with adults and peers, as well as the organization of systematic training in the classroom are recognized as the source of the development of the preschool child.

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